

Influence of Anionic Surfactant Aggregates in the Reaction of Benzoate Ion and Phenacyl Bromide

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The reaction between phenacyl bromide and benzoate ion has been followed in aqueous methanol and aqueous acetone solvent systems in the presence of anionic surfactant aggregates of sodium dodecyl sulphate (NaLS). Electrostatic and hydrophobic effects both are found to operate in this reaction. Increasing aggregate concentration or addition of electrolytes decreased the electrostatic effect. Consequently, the rate was found to increase due to a pronounced hydrophobic influence. The values of cooperativity index (n), $\log[D]_{1,0}$ and K_D have been calculated.

BINDING at a micellar surface resembles the behaviour at the interface of proteins, biological membranes and receptors. Similarities between the folded tertiary structure of proteins and micelles¹⁻⁴ have aroused interest in the use of micellar systems as models for enzyme catalysis.

Micelles are capable of forming a new reaction medium and can concentrate reagents at the detergent-water interface^{1,2}. Generally, the cationic micelles are found to catalyze and the anionic micelles retard an anion-dipole reaction because hydrophobic and coulombic interactions play their respective roles in bringing the reactants together for reaction. Though surfactants form globular micelles in water, Parfitt and Wood⁵ have shown that no such micelles are formed at high alcohol concentration. However, some kind of aggregate is expected in a mixed solvent system. The present study was, therefore, undertaken to observe the influence of an aggregate, if any, on the reaction of an ion and a molecule, both containing hydrophobic centres.

Experimental

Materials: Sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS) was purified by the method of Duynstee and Grunwald⁶. Water was distilled twice before use. Acetone and methanol were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade and used without further purification. Phenacyl bromide was prepared and purified by the method of Rather and Ried⁷. All the salts were crystallised and dried before use.

Kinetics: The reaction between phenacyl bromide (0.008 M) and benzoate (0.16 M) in presence of surfactant was followed by chilling 5 ml aliquote in 10 ml 6 N nitric acid and 5 ml 0.02 M silver nitrate solution and titrating the liberated bromide ion argentometrically using ferric alum indicator⁸. The second-order rate constants were computed by a least-squares method using the bimolecular rate equation,

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t(b-a)} \log \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$$

Product: The reaction between benzoate ion and phenacyl bromide can be represented by Scheme 1. The product of the reaction was isolated

and on analysis was found to be phenacyl benzoate, yield 70%, m.p. 128-129°; ir (nujol) 1705

(>C=O in $\text{-OCC}_6\text{H}_5$), 1685 (>C=O in $C_6H_5\text{-C(=O)-CH}_2\text{-}$); 2850 cm^{-1} (w, $\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$ stretch); ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) δ 5.50 (2H, s), 7.41 (5H, m), 8.01 (5H, m).

Results and Discussion

The values of second-order rate constants for the reaction of phenacyl bromide and benzoate ion in methanol-water (40 : 60 v/v) and acetone-water (72 : 28 v/v) are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The rate constants in acetone-water is larger than in methanol-water system.

Influence of surfactant: The reaction between phenacyl bromide and benzoate ion has been studied

TABLE 1—OBSERVED SECOND-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE AND BENZOATE ION IN THE PRESENCE OF NaLS IN METHANOL-WATER (40 : 60 v/v)

[PhBr]=0.008 M, $[C_6H_5COO^-]=0.016$ M, Temp.=35°			
$10^3 \times [NaLS]$ M	$10^4 \times k_2$, M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	$10^3 \times [NaLS]$	$10^4 \times k_2$, M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
0.0	8.74	4.0	3.25
0.81	6.58	4.5	4.51
1.5	4.25	5.0	5.01
2.0	3.40	6.0	6.52
2.5	2.77	7.0	6.93
3.0	1.92	8.1	7.11
3.5	2.31		

TABLE 2—OBSERVED SECOND-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE AND BENZOATE ION IN THE PRESENCE OF NaLS IN ACETONE-WATER (72 : 28 v/v)

[PhBr]=0.008 M, [C₆H₅COO⁻]=0.016 M, Temp.=35°

10 ³ × [NaLS] M	10 ⁴ × k _a M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	10 ³ × [NaLS] M	10 ⁴ × k _a M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
0.0	35.92	3.24	18.74
0.5	29.35	4.05	25.43
0.81	25.84	4.86	31.63
1.5	24.37	6.48	38.23
2.0	21.79	9.72	39.76

with varying concentrations of NaLS. The plot of k_a vs detergent concentration describes a curve with a minimum at the detergent concentration of 0.03 M.

Parfitt and Wood⁵ showed that at a mole fraction of 0.12 of methanol in water, the aggregation number of NaLS 'micelles' was 23. At a mole fraction of 0.27 there were no micelles. In the present study a mole fraction of 0.23 has been used and therefore an average aggregation number of less than 23 (62 in water) is expected. Tanford's packing model does not predict a spherical micelle with such a low aggregation number.

In the microenvironment of the aggregate solution, the hydrophobic attraction of the hydrocarbon chain and the coulombic repulsion of the anionic head groups of the aggregate influence the incorporation of the reactants. Phenacyl bromide being a non-ionic molecule having a hydrophobic part is therefore incorporated in the aggregate phase relatively to a larger extent than the benzoate anion. Thus the effective concentration of phenacyl bromide decreases in the solution progressively with increasing detergent concentration, resulting in the descending limb of the curve. With increasing concentration of the surfactant, the concentration of the counterions (Na⁺) also increases, which may neutralise the net negative charge of the anionic head and thus facilitate further incorporation of benzoate ion accounting for the ascending limb of the curve.

Salt effect : Since the descending portion of the curve can also be ascribed to an ionic strength effect due to the presence of the amphiphiles, a salt effect has been studied in the absence of surfactant. The rate was initially suppressed at a salt concentration of ≈0.1 M and remained constant thereafter. The suppression, however, was much less compared to decrease in micellar system.

If the explanation proposed earlier for the ascending limb is tenable, the presence of unreactive counterions would accelerate the reaction from the beginning in presence of anionic micelles. The salt effect has therefore been studied at a fixed surfactant concentration of 0.03 M and a positive salt effect has been noted.

The reaction has also been studied at a fixed salt concentration of 0.2 M Li₂SO₄ and at different surfactant concentrations. The descending portion

TABLE 3—OBSERVED SECOND-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE AND BENZOATE ION IN THE PRESENCE OF NaLS AND INORGANIC SALTS IN METHANOL-WATER (40 : 60 v/v) AT 35°

[PhBr]=0.008 M, [C₆H₅COO⁻]=0.016 M, [NaLS]=0.03 M

	[Salt] M			
	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.04
	10 ⁴ × k _a , M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹			
KNO ₃	1.92	12.21	13.43	14.09
NaNO ₃		9.95	11.98	12.21
Li ₂ SO ₄		7.50	9.62	10.26
Na ₂ SO ₄		8.98	10.18	10.88
K ₂ SO ₄		9.86	11.09	10.88
MgSO ₄		4.08	4.81	5.54

of the curve has been found to be absent. The positive influence of the salt with respect to cation is in the order K⁺ > Na⁺ > Li⁺ > Mg²⁺ and for anion it is NO₃⁻ > SO₄²⁻. These salts therefore are V-type activators.

Treatment of data : The kinetic model used in this study to describe the dependence of rate constant on detergent concentration is based on the reaction mechanism proposed by Bruice *et al*⁹ and applied by Piszkiwics¹⁰ to available data on micellar catalyzed reactions. According to this model, it is assumed that a number of detergent molecules, D, and the substrate, S, aggregate to form the catalytic complex, D_nS, which then react to yield the product. This is represented by Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

In this scheme, K_D is the dissociation constant of the substrate-aggregate complex back to its free components, k_o is the rate constant in absence of surfactant and k_m is the rate constant within the aggregate. The observed rate constant can therefore be expressed as a function of the detergent concentration, [D], by equation 1, which is rewritten in the form of equation 2.

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_m[D]^n + k_o K_D}{K_D + [D]^n} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\log \left(\frac{k_{obs} - k_o}{k_m - k_{obs}} \right) = n \log [D] - \log K_D \quad \dots (2)$$

A plot of log $\left(\frac{k_{obs} - k_o}{k_m - k_{obs}} \right)$ vs log [D] is linear for

the NaLS inhibited/catalyzed reaction of phenacyl bromide and benzoate ion with a slope of n and intercept log K_D. The value of dissociation constant, K_D, has been calculated by a least-squares method from the intercept. The maximum/minimum

rate constant obtained in presence of detergent is taken as the value for k_m . A linear reciprocal plot of rate constant vs detergent concentration has been prepared and the value of k_a at $\frac{1}{[NaLS]}=0$ has been

taken as the value for k_m . This analysis was applied only to the portion of the curve prior to the maximum or minimum.

The least-squares values of n , K_D and r (correlation coefficient) are given in Table 4. Examination

TABLE 4—CALCULATED VALUES OF n , K_D , k_m/k_0 AND r IN THE REACTION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE (0.008 M) AND BENZOATE ION (0.016 M) WITH VARYING [NaLS]

Temp °C	n	$10^3 \times K_D$, M	$-\log [D]_{50}$	k_m/k_0	r
35 ^a	1.72	33.5	0.86	0.52	0.9491
35 ^b	2.03	8.62	1.02	0.22	0.9903
35 ^c	1.09	45.50	1.23	3.16	0.9861

^a In acetone-water (72 : 28 v/v) in absence of Li_2SO_4 .

^b In methanol-water (40 : 60 v/v) in absence of Li_2SO_4 .

^c In methanol-water (40 : 60 v/v) in presence of 0.2 M Li_2SO_4 .

of these data indicates a decrease in the value of $\log [D]_{50}$ and n by the addition of electrolyte whereas a change in the solvent system decreases the $\log [D]_{50}$ and increases n . Since n is the cooperativity index, addition of electrolyte and change in solvent system interfere with the cooperative nature of the complex, D_nS .

The results presented in this paper have led to suggest the existence of an aggregate system, the behaviour of which conforms to the model presented by Piszkiwicz.

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References

1. E. H. CORDES and C. GITLER, *Prog. Bioorg. Chem.*, 1973, **2**, 1.
2. J. H. FENDLER and E. J. FENDLER "Catalysis in Micellar and Macromolecular Systems", Academic Press, New York, N. Y., 1975.
3. C. A. BUNTON, "Micellar Reactions", in "Applications of Biomedical Systems in Chemistry", Part-II, (Ed.) J. B. JONES, Wiley, New York, N. Y., 1976, Chapter 4.
4. (a) W. KAUFMAN, *Adv. Protein Chem.*, 1959, **14**, 1.
(b) M. F. PERUTZ, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1965, **13**, 646.
(c) C. A. BUNTON, L. ROBINSON and M. F. STAM, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1971, 121.
(d) P. MUKHERJEE and A. RAY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2144.
5. G. D. PARFITT and J. A. WOOD, *Kolloid Z. Z. Polymer*, 1969, **229**, 55.
6. E. F. DUYNSTEE and E. GRUNWALD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4540, 4542.
7. A. RATHER and P. RIED, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 75.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green and Co. Ltd., London, 1961, p. 264.
9. T. O. BRUCE, J. KATZHEIMER and L. B. FEDOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1333.
10. D. PISZKIWICZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 1550.